

GENDER RELATIONS IN ICT FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN FINE ARTS EDUCATION IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

The trend of gender imbalances cut across every human endeavour including education sector. The need to integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in teaching and learning process by educators of fine arts irrespective of their gender for driving sustainable development cannot be overemphasis. This paper focus on gender relations in ICT for sustainable development in fine arts education. Pervious relevant studies on gender balance, ICT, sustainable development and fine arts education were reviewed using thematic approach. The outcome of review shows that there exist gender imbalances among fine arts educators regarding the use of ICTs. The integration of ICTs into fine arts education can lead to desirable sustainable development. However, technophobia, digital divide, and gender stereotype were the factors responsible for low female utilization of ICTs in fine arts education. The paper concludes that balance gender representation among fine arts educators could lead to sustainable development through job opportunity, creation of serenity environment, promotion of tourism attractions and engineering the environmental conservative. The study recommends that the ministry of education in collaboration with ICTs experts should organised seminar training for female educators to boost their ICT skills and utilization for fine arts education.

Keywords: Gender Balance, ICT, Sustainable Development, and Fine arts Education

Introduction

Global trends of attaining sustainable development have led to the identification of the need for even representation of people irrespective of gender. It is a fact that women comprise almost half of the world population. However, the global economic distribution pattern shows that women hold less

than one percent of global capital. It also, remains the fact that global sharing of responsibilities favour men than women, with women shouldering various categories of assignments from domestic roles to economic drivers. Women serving as first teacher and nurturer for children back at home, playing role of home maintainers as well as taking central role in global food production. Nevertheless, women are made to have limited access to personal assets and mostly prevented from gaining skills that can enhance their expertness in the profession of their choice (UNDP, 2018).

The debate supporting or countering gender imbalances across the globe remains unquenched. However, the recent evidences have shown that the intensity and dynamism of discussing women as well as gender issues have changed with more and more awareness is on-going, attracting global political interests, policy and legal backing. Both at international and local scenes, seminars, workshops and other capacity building are being held with focus on gender aspects, especially women on their representation, participation and advancement across various aspects of life. At some levels, women are denied access to technical skills and adoption of technology as well as witnessing strategic high rate of unemployment. Therefore, it is pertinent to look into issues of gender imbalance in our society to attain sustainable development, especially, concerning the gender balance of usage of ICTs as precision tool in professions such as fine arts. The fine arts is a broad profession that primarily knowing for aesthetics or creative expression with slight different to decorative art or applied art, which also has to serve some practical function, such as pottery or most metalwork. Artist communicates through their virtual expressions using various medium like water colours, oils pastel and acrylic colours (Okon, 2021). Art as professional is universal language that permeates every civilization and is essential for everyday life and defines the history of any society.

Historically, the five main fine arts were painting, sculpture, architecture, music, and poetry, with performing arts including theatre and dance (Markus, 2023). In practice, outside education, the concept is typically only applied to the visual arts. However, the recent gain in technology development such as advancement in the information communication technologies has provides avenues for different professions to take their skills to another levels. Using ICT for fine arts as profession and for teaching fine arts in education sector is a unique approach that supposed to favour professionals in the field irrespective of their gender. Various evidences have shown that

there are gaps in the utilization of ICTs based on various factors including gender. In Nigeria, arts and artistic works had been the part of national history that has both male and female as key players. Almost all regions of Nigeria have historical legacy showcasing the artistic works of their ancestors and modern artists. The Nigerian education system recognises teaching of Fine arts at various level, while at tertiary institutions students are allow to specialize in the field of fine arts as profession. Thus, in the various classrooms including fine arts classes, the adoption of ICTs for teaching and learning take central stage as Nigeria is moving toward modern practices in education. However, there are early evidences such as Sayfullaev (2019) and Markus (2023) shown that adoption of ICTs for teaching and learning process in Nigeria schools is low. Faith and Daniel (2021) and Adeoye (2018) pointers show that female teaching staff are less participatory according to gender.

The low utilization of ICTs could deter the intents to utilize every professional skill in Nigeria education such as fine arts, for the attainment of sustainable development. Not only the level of utilization of ICTs could be worrisome the extent both gender within the academic staff as well as professional in education utilize ICTs could define the overall achievement in the bids for the attainment of sustainable development in Nigeria. Therefore, it become pertinent to seek the gender related issues in ICT for sustainable development in fine arts education in Nigeria.

Gender and ICT usage

The rate of ICT usage varied across various diversity. Specifically, the proportionate of usage of ICTs among gender differed significantly in favour of male. Adeoye (2018) expressed that despite of the fact that information and communication technology has gained considerable attention in various sectors, there are still individual differences in its use and relevant skills. Likewise, it is no more news that ICT has played major roles in development of different professions but the rate at which the development is being recorded per profession differs. In Nigeria today, the ICT applications are almost everywhere, such as education, health, banking, business, politics and security sectors as well as in fine arts as profession. Majuto and Gilbert (2018) expressed that there is a small and positive, yet not significant, effect of gender on ICTs usage among professionals in favour of male. Thus, as the use of ICTs is becoming one of the most fundamental building blocks of contemporary civilization in a relatively short period, the gap is yet to be covered effectively among genders.

Several studies on ICTs usage show that numbers of Nigerians using ICTs have increased significantly but those using ICTs as professional tool are less, while huge proportion of Nigerians use ICTs to seek social information. The demographic analysis of ICTs usage among Nigerians show that young people use more ICTs than elders; female are more on social media for non-career related information than male (Mahmood, 2019). While significant progress has been made in the ICTs usage, there remains a severe territorial and gender technological inequality. Many studies exist that contradict each other on the matter of gender differences in ICT use, while some studies have shown differing results in that some claim benefits for females. In contrast, others offer benefits for boys (Faith and Daniel, 2021). The scenario of ICT usage according to gender among Nigerians remains largely in favour of male and gaps seems further widen among professionals. Likewise, the rate of usage of ICTs for career development varied according gender also in favour of male professionals.

ICT in Fine arts Education

ICT has changed the way most people do business, including those in the art field. Not only do artists, animators, photographers and filmmakers use ICT devices such as computers to create their art, they use them for much more. Truly, ICTs and other modern technologies might be arguably running the show of modern invention and innovative development. Thus, integrating both the ICTs and fine arts could lead to sustainable development. Malero, Ismail and Manyilizu (2019) expressed that both the scientific and technological skills are not the only forces driving innovation. Creativity and the involvement of society play a major role in the innovation process. Integration of the arts is an essential and fruitful component within innovative worlds. The linkage between ICTs and fine arts has expanded the opportunities for artists as well as researchers. The constant appropriation of new technologies by artists allows them to go further in actively participating in society. By using ICT as their medium of expression, artists are able to prototype solutions, while creating new products and making new economic, social and business models. Malero *et al.* (2019) ICT is engulfing all aspects of contemporary life, and the art world is no exception. Analog art forms such as painting, sculpture and film-based photography are more frequently either combined with or replaced by digital processes.

Even in areas such as documentation of art, digital technology is having an impact. Many artists combine digital technology in their art process, either in creating the artwork or in using digital technology to create a finished piece. Artists are now incorporating the web either to make their art or distribute it. Some artworks now only exist as online entities, and have no physical presence except for what one can see on the computer screen. Digital are now combined in arts for the creation of modern work. For instance, a painting done in acrylic can be scanned electronically, rendering a digital image, which can be manipulated with a photo editing program. A high-quality giclee print of the painting can then be printed from digital image. Some giclee prints can be printed onto primed canvas to re-create the look of the original painting. Many artists use computer tools to either capture or create images which are then produced in analog form. Thus, the advent of ICT has enhanced the possibility to preserve artworks in digital format as well as speed up art distribution and professional promotion via the web.

As efforts to emphasize the effective integration between ICTs and Art, the European Commission in 2020 launched a program called STARTS meaning Science, Technology and the Arts. This is the amalgamation between ICT and Art. Such program justifies the contribution of ICTs as precision tools for fine arts (Daniel, Carlos and João, 2022). Mahmood (2019) expressed that most designs that were previously conceived as impossible are now possible and feasible through ICTs. Specifically, the STARTS program was meant to remove the boundaries between art and engineering in order to stimulate creativity and innovation. Mohd-Khairezan, and Wing (2017) maintained that majority of high-tech companies have embrace the arts to boost their innovation capacity. This is done by hire or creating fine arts section where idea can be demonstrated, fine-tuned, modelled and designed before implemented. Therefore, the artists give their professionalism in turning idea to reality with help of ICTs devices. Thus, ICTs has many inputs in developing fine arts.

ICTs can be used as instructional materials or teaching aids for fine arts education at school. Udi in Okon (2021) affirms this as a model of instruction tagged “Pastel Painting Package (PPCIP) is designed to improve student academic achievement using computer power point to present lessons electronically. The main role of ICT integration in education is to create new efficient education capacities. ICT offers telepresence, immersivity and virtual reality that are of great potentialities issues offer for a new way of teaching and learning fine arts in the classroom. The question is how many of our educators

are aware of these unique ICT's features? And how many could make use of them effectively? Teo and Schaik (2019) expressed that most teachers are yet to maximise the use of ICTs for teaching at schools. This could also be applicable to fine arts and the scenario could go lower when consider female fine arts educators. Mohd-Khairezan, and Wing (2017) found that the proportion of teachers using ICTs for teaching is low, though mostly among male teachers. Thus, using ICTs for teaching fine arts by both male and female teachers can transform traditional fine arts and reposition the teaching and learning of fine arts as subject in the school.

Fine arts and Sustainable Development

Sustainable development is one of the greatest challenges facing humanity. The need for stable development remains one of main focus at international, national and sub-national levels. The sustainable development implies an approach that meets the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Since this report, scientific evidence has multiplied to demonstrate that human behaviour is responsible for deterioration in our earth systems (Villaespesa, 2019). Catarina and Perrotta (2020) expressed that fine arts remains one of the testament to human creativity and during these times of economic uncertainty and global financial crisis; human need creative solutions to human scale problems such as sustainability. There is a substantial need for innovation and creativity in design of human-nature relationships, by inventing sustainable lifestyles and enterprises (Teo and Schaik, 2019). Using art as a means for achieving sustainability opens up a controversial debate in the contemporary philosophy.

The future associative challenge for sustainable development, likely to evolve through need for sustainable lifestyles, emotional balance, ethical engineering practices, safety of natural environment, interpersonal and organisational relationships. Thus, the roles of fine arts in attainment of sustainability is to offer experiential relationship among human, organisations and nature. The artists, especially female artists will need to take holistic approach that will create awareness of ecosystems and generate passion for sustainable living, as well as reminding individual about personal responsibility for ecological action, and collaborative problem solving. Thus, the sustainable development through fine arts will imply using all materials that will not only offer safety of ecosystem but encourage members of society from further harming our environment. Teaching fine arts in school should

encourage young male and female artists to use eco-friendly materials and safety technology. The adoption of ICTs as well as other modern technology for teaching and practices fine arts could contribute decisively to competitiveness, sustainability, social inclusion and gender representation that has been the target for many international bodies.

Fine arts can be taught in the school and practices within our society to serve as vehicle for human emotions and passion toward preventing our degrading society. To make fine arts serves as driver for passion and development, all hands have to be on desk, the utilization of ICTs in fine arts has to be improved from current state. The passion for safer environment that could be driven by fine arts through ICTs is expected to be those represent form of human emotional intelligence. Thus, fine arts could act as the repository of human emotions, and aesthetic inquiry that can valuable infuse passion in our pursuit of sustainability (Wang, 2018). Also, fine arts stands to offer sustainable development through job opportunity for all, irrespective of gender, especially when female artists show efficiency in the usage of ICTs for their artistry design.

Challenges Facing Female Artists in Usage of ICT

Adoption of ICT for many activities is not without challenges. ICT is yet to be maximally integrated into daily activities in most government offices, private firm and individuals in Nigeria. The scenario for low ICT adoption could be more significant when comparing the effect of gender on ICT utilization in respect to their profession. One of the challenges facing women in the adoption of ICTs in their activities is the factor known as technological divide. Villaespesa (2019) expressed that despite huge investment in the technology across the globe the gender digital divide index is still relatively high, especially among people living within developing nations. It is saddened that despite of the fact that the world is increasingly digital, the digital gender gap is still high. The yearly data show a persistent gender divide in access to the information and communication technologies (ICTs) that promote social and economic growth.

Nwasinachi and Bernadette (2014) show that women are less likely to know how to operate a smartphone, navigate the internet, use social media and understand how to safeguard information in digital mediums, especially, when considering the abilities that underlie life and work tasks as relevant to people of all ages. Women in numerous countries are 25% less likely than men to know

how to leverage ICT for basic purposes including teaching. UNESCO estimates that men are around four times more likely than women to have advanced ICT skills such as the ability to programme computers or coordinate high level lesson delivery (Loveless, 2016). Across G20 countries 7% of ICT patents are generated by women while the global average is at 2% (Wang, 2018). Also, women are disadvantage to the adoption of ICTs due to technophobia. Punter, Meelissen and Glas (2017) expressed that technophobia is an extreme fear of technology. Some individual may doubt self on the best uses of ICTs and other technology, thereby simply ignore it. Though, technophobia is more than resistance to learning new technology. Rather, people with the condition may be obsess over technology. Or, they may go to great lengths to avoid incorporating technology into their lives. This scenario could occur even among teaching staff at various academic level, where there may be fear of how to use ICTs for teaching and learning activities such as fine arts education. Nwasinachi and Bernadette (2014) expressed technophobia may not necessarily mean usage denial but fear of failure.

In many societies, gender equality does not translate into gender equality in digital realms and digital professions. The persistence of growing digital skills gender gaps, even in countries that rank among top economic development of the world are not spare of gender disparities in use of ICTs and other digital devices. The persistent gender gap in technologies adoption demonstrates a need for interventions that cultivate the digital skills for women and girls. For most countries, the primary barriers for women regarding access to digital technology are costs which heighten the unaffordability followed by illiteracy and lack of digital skills. Women and girls may struggle to access public ICT facilities due to unsafe roads, limits on their freedom of movement, or because the facilities themselves are considered unsuitable for women (Loveless, 2016). Women may not have the financial independence needed to purchase digital technology or pay for internet connectivity. Digital access, even when available, may be controlled and monitored by men or limited to 'walled gardens' containing a limited selection of content. Fears concerning safety and harassment both online and offline may also inhibit many women and girls from benefiting from or even wanting to use ICTs (Gebhardt, et al. 2020). In many contexts, women and girls face concerns of physical violence if they own or borrow digital devices, which in some cases lead to their using the devices in secret, making them more vulnerable to online threats and making it difficult to gain digital skills (Nwasinachi and Bernadette, 2014).

The stereotype of technology as a male domain is common in many contexts and affect girls' confidence in their digital skills from a young age. In the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) countries, 0.5% of girls aspire towards ICT-related careers at age 15, versus 5% of boys (Gebhardt *et al.*, 2020). This was not always the case. Fraillon *et al.* (2019) accounted that at the beginning of electronic computing following the Second World War, software programming in industrialized countries was considered 'women's work'. Managers of early technology firms allowed women well-suited for programming because of stereotypes characterizing them as meticulous and good at following step-by-step directions. Women, including many women of colour, flocked to jobs in the computer industry because it was seen as more meritocratic than other fields. As computers became integrated into people's daily life, it was noticed that programmers had influence. Consequently, women were systematically being pushed out and the field became more male-dominated (Fraillon *et al.*, 2019).

Effective approach for gender equity in ICTs usage in fine arts education

There are series of suggestions, approaches, deliberations and options that had been earlier offered through empirical studies as means of closing the gender gap in the use of ICTs as instructional materials in schools as well as using ICTs for professional practices. The following are some of the most common suggestions or approaches to reduce the ICTs gender gap.

1. Dedicated ICT training for female educators

Training refers to educational activities meant to enhance the knowledge and skills of employees while providing information and instruction on how to better perform specific tasks. According to Zhang and Aikman (2017) dedicated training can be perceived as a short-term reactive process meant to guide individual toward competency and effective skills. Thus, gaining ICT skills could require a dedicated approach to enhance the overall operative skills of individual especially female educators. There are earlier empirical evidences pointed at the fact that most ICTs compliant trainings are dominated by male participants (Olowoyeye, 2019; Toluwani, 2020). Thus, reversing the rate at which individual are being trained on ICTs require dedicated ICTs trainings targeting female participants this will create rooms for proper grooming as well as allow free interaction among participants which may somehow difficult when having both gender as participants. In this case, the

dedicated training for female is aimed toward developing additional ICTs skills for the female. Especially, in the teaching services, female educators may be subjected to various ICT trainings purposely to enhance their performance as teachers as well as their productivity.

Likewise, Zhang and Aikman (2017) argued that training for educator is not meant only for personal development but also for overall enhancement of job productivity in educational institution where they are serving. It should be cleared to both the teaching staff and educational planners that training directly served double purposes of enhancing individual competency as well as promoting overall productivity in education sector. There is no doubt, that the excellence of a fine arts teacher irrespective of gender determines the success of a school and the quality of knowledge and experience of students that it produces (Hawlina, *et al*, 2019). The fine arts teachers must have dedicated skills that can spur-on the performance spirit to accomplish every task designed to impart valuable knowledge for students. David and Cátia-Diogo, (2020) found that highly professional teachers that mastered the use of modern technology such as ICTs mostly have a profound effect on student achievement. A superior teacher should master the entire curriculum and be capable of choosing important aspects that should be focused on. Toluwani (2020) claimed that teacher preparedness through various trainings directly affect contribution toward students' knowledge development and academic achievements. An ideal teacher irrespective of gender is expected to use any procedure and devices including ICTs to provide clear explanations and descriptions for the learners.

Haroon and Peters (2020) found that female teachers need to be subjected to various trainings on technology usage in order to attain modern educational innovations to execute improved teaching concepts and help them become experts in delivering classroom instructions. According to Hawlina *et al*. (2019), developing student creativity provides students with additional opportunities to explore and explain their learning materials required competent teachers in all intelligent dimensions including usage of ICTs. In addition, the advent of modern communication technology has changed the roles of teachers from serving as classroom role model for students to overall educational embodiment. Today, teachers need special skills such as ICTs skills to augment instructional materials if need arise, teachers need to coordinate students both near and far, virtually or physically. Above all, efforts to improve the use of ICTs for pedagogical activities among female fine arts education

have to be strategic, direct and dedicated and all female staff irrespective of their level have to be supported to participate.

2. Provision of ICTs Facilities in Schools

If there is anything that deny teaching staff from adoption ICTs for teaching and learning activities at school such things must be lack of ICTs facilities. In most of the schools, the provision for adoption of ICTs for teaching and learning remains paper document, while the actualization of policy cannot be seen anywhere. Thus, Haroon and Peters (2020) suggested that to adopt ICTs for teaching and learning processes, the school authorities as well as government have to provide necessary ICTs facilities and it has to be accessible for all staff irrespective of gender. The scenario in most of fine arts studios and the respective classrooms showed that largely the ICTs facilities are yet to be prioritised as most of old features remain unchanged. To encourage usage of ICTs among fine arts staff irrespective of gender the provision for ICTs have to be adequate and supports for its utilization have to be clearly provided.

Kenning (2019) noted that in some cases the facilities favouring usage of ICTs are provided but adequacy remain a major challenge and in some instances the female staff need to rival the male counterpart on limited available ICTs facilities. In some schools' ICTs are strictly provided for science students while those offering other program such as fine arts, history, geography, banking among others are not favoured. Such favourism distribution of ICTs facilities have huge effect on female usage of ICTs for teaching and learning activities in fine arts or not. If any school want to encourage ICTs utilization among its staff irrespective of gender, unit or department such school must ensure adequate provision of ICTs to every department and section as well as offer other necessary supports for the staff. The rivalry between male and female staff regarding who use what have to be addressed holistically. Most of the earlier works on ICTs provision and utilization suggested that ICTs provision was low. Olowoyeye (2019) found that level of ICTs integration for teaching and learning process in Ghana education system is low majorly attributable to poor wireless connectivity. Likewise, in Kenya Kupaysinovna (2021) found that the challenges facing implementation of ICT in public secondary schools was due to high cost of acquisition and maintenance of ICT equipment as well as lack of electricity. Also, Faith and Daniel (2021) in Tanzania established that schools did not have enough ICT devices for effective integration of ICT.

3. Effective gender-balanced partnership among staff on ICT usage

Teaching profession is full of passionate educators, therefore, collaboration among them is a unique force that propel every teacher to perform effectively and professionally. Otakhor (2017) expressed that teachers usually find themselves planning, organizing materials, making and grading assignments, but have to stand in front of a class alone. At some point loneliness within the classroom could affect teachers' ability to coordinate the lesson not because of incompetency but due to needs for hand-on activities within the classroom that likely require assistance of other competent hands. In such scenario, the use of ICTs as pedagogical tools could require other supportive staff that give hand where and when necessary. Thus, the effective use of ICTs may demand collaboration among staff irrespective of gender. Portnova (2019) expressed that teachers of both sexes, need to frequently interact with other colleagues as means of sharing experiences, idea and planning ahead of lesson. Kupaysinovna (2021) noted that collaboration among staff of both genders does not point at weakness of particular sex but indicating the fact that none is an island of knowledge and skills.

To ensure effective use of ICTs for lesson delivery, assessment and other possible activities, teachers of both gender need to be innovative, collaborate, share ideas as well as given helping hands when required. Many aspects and forms of collaboration, both formal and informal, can contribute to student success and decrease teacher burnout. The incidents of rivalry, segregation and selfishness among teaching staff is unaccepted, as it deterred their overall achievement as academic staff and limit their inputs toward learners' achievement. Using ICTs as instructional materials in fine arts classes could be challenging due to nature of classroom arrangement. Teacher collaboration provides fellow educators opportunities to meet, share insights, create cohesive plans, and work together effectively (Kenning, 2019). Offering a variety of teacher collaboration opportunities builds strong educational communities and also well-connected and supportive colleagues.

Conclusion

Evidences from reviewed in this paper have reiterated the fact that there exist gender imbalances among fine arts educators regarding the use of ICTs as tool to drive the desired sustainable development. Specifically, this paper has established the fact that fine arts shared success history with humanity and has

been the driver for innovation and creativity prior arrival of modern technology. Thus, the current advent of ICT can only make the teaching and learning including practices of fine arts more effective. Also, this paper has shown that there are gender disparities in rate of ICT usage among fine arts educators, with female educators having minimal utilization. Technophobia, technology divide, and gender stereotype were the factors responsible for low female utilization of ICTs in fine arts education. Meanwhile, this paper has established the fact that fine arts education when integrated ICT can sufficiently drive sustainable development through job opportunity, creation of serenity environment, promotion of tourism attractions and engineering the environmental conservative.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are suggested:

1. The ministry of education in collaboration with ICTs experts should organised seminar training for female educators to boost their ICT skills and utilization for fine arts education
2. The Nigerian government should ensure that schools are equipped with necessary ICT facilities including alternative power supply that can support female fine arts educator for utilization of ICT for teaching and learning process
3. The school authorities should facilitate the collaboration among educators of both gender on the use of ICT. Sharing of idea and the experiences among educators which could improve their reflective teaching skills regarding utilization of ICT in classrooms.
4. There is need for review of curriculum for fine arts education to accommodate the use of ICTs for teaching and learning activities, such will encourage fine arts educators irrespective of gender to use ICT.

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